

Correlate the Small Punch Test as a substitute for the Tensile test for copper and its alloys using Finite Element Analysis.

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Abstract

The Small Punch technique is a miniature test used mostly for irradiated materials or when the test material is scarcely available. The main aim of small specimen mechanics is to figure out the mechanical behavior with a great reduction or small volume of material. This document emphasizes the development of correlations between mechanical characteristics determined from small punch tests and uniaxial tensile tests. Recommended techniques for specimen design, specimen preparation, experimental design, experimental implementation, and data analysis are used according to ASTM SPT 888. The test involves bending the disk symmetrically about the center, producing a simple, axisymmetric stress state. First, the right conditions were simulated via Finite Element Analysis and then stress and deformation analysis were done for all the specimens, and the results were obtained. These equations are applied to all the copper alloys at a temperature of 295 K. The equations can be used to determine the uniaxial tensile stress-strain behavior of copper and its alloys.

Keywords: Small Punch Test, Finite Element Analysis, FEA, Copper, ASTM SPT 888.

1. Introduction

Residual lifetime assessment of high-temperature industrial components requires accurate mechanical property data, which is challenging to obtain without compromising structural integrity. Traditional uniaxial tests (tensile, fatigue) may not capture biaxial stress behavior critical for components like pressure vessels (Matocha, 2007). The small punch test (SPT) addresses this by using miniature specimens (typically 8 mm diameter, 0.5 mm thick) extracted directly from components, enabling property evaluation without significant damage (Lucon, 2020).

SPT estimates tensile strength, fracture toughness, and creep behavior through biaxial loading and requires significantly less material than standard tests, allowing repeated sampling for condition monitoring (Wen, 2016). However, specimen miniaturization increases scatter due to localized defects, and empirical correlations between SPT parameters and conventional mechanical properties are required, which vary by material class (Lucon, 2020).

Current research focuses on improving SPT correlations for diverse materials, particularly additively manufactured alloys, where anisotropy complicates analysis. Reliable implementation could optimize maintenance schedules and extend component lifespans in power generation and chemical industries.

2. Experimental Procedure

The principle of the small punch test is that a small hemispherical tip or a ball (“punch”) is pushed through a disc-shaped specimen along its axis of symmetry. SP testing can be conducted as creep tests, in which a constant force is applied, and displacement is measured over time or as tensile/fracture tests, in which a constant displacement rate is applied to the punch and force is recorded over time.

SPTs have been performed on different test specimens of copper and its alloys. The SPT specimens had a nominal dimension of a 3mm radius disk and 0.25 mm thickness, which was carefully obtained. A tungsten carbide ball of 1mm diameter is placed over the specimen. The punch is then inserted into the lower die.

Fig: Left - Specimen support configuration and loading scheme in test set-up of SPT, Right - 3D view of the small punch test fixture.

2.1 Chemical Composition & Mechanical Properties

The metals under study are Copper and its various alloys. The chemical composition and plastic properties of these alloys are as follows:

Name and Treatment	Plastic Properties (Uni-axial)		Composition					
	Tensile Strength (psi)	Yield Strength (psi)	Pb	Fe	Sn	Zn	Ni	P
C102 - Oxygen Free (Cold drawn 60%)	48,400	46,800	4	4	1		4	1
C122 - Phosphorus Deoxidized, High Residual Phosphorus (Annealed)	31,300	6,700	0.0002	0	0	0.001		0
C150 - Zirconium Copper (Cold drawn, aged)	64,450	59,600	Similar to that of Oxygen Free with Zr added					
C230 - Red Brass, 85% (Cold drawn 14%)	40,400	13,000		0		15.33		
C464 - Naval Brass (Annealed)	63,300	31,000	0.09	0	1	39.71		
C510 - Phosphor Bronze, 5% A	77,400	72,000	0.02	0	5	0.05		0

(Cold drawn 85%, spring)							
C614 - Aluminum Bronze D (Annealed)	83,200	59,400		2			
C655 - High Silicon Bronze A (Annealed, soft)	61,400	24,200	0.01	0			0.04
C715 - Copper Nickel 30% (Annealed)	57,800	18,700	< 0.01	1	< 0.01	0.04	30.05

Table: Copper Specimen Material Properties and Chemical Composition

2.2 Curve Fitting

Curve fitting is required to get the relationship between true stress and true plastic strain. Here, the precision of the True Plastic Strain curve is obtained by observing the fit in the power law equations, and it is recognized by R2, which is the Coefficient of Determination. If R2 > 90%, then the curve fits accurately on a power law; thus, the result obtained is good.

$$\text{Power Law: } \sigma = K\epsilon^n$$

(σ – Stress, ϵ - True Plastic Strain, K - Strength Coefficient, n- Strain Hardening Exponent)

Below is the example for getting the power law for C102 – Oxygen free (Cold Drawn 60%). Here, y = stress and x = true plastic strain.

Fig. Example of curve fitting using power law for C102 – Oxygen free (Cold drawn 60%)

After the relation between true stress and true plastic strain is available, the following inputs were given during the analysis of the metals:

Name	Power law (Stress= $K*(\text{True Plastic Strain})^n$)	Young's Modulus (Gpa)	Poisson's Ratio
C102 - Oxygen Free (Cold drawn 60%)	$y = 441.54x^{0.0734}$ $R^2 = 0.9783$	119.28	0.31
C122 - Phosphorus Deoxidized, High Residual Phosphorus (Annealed)	$y = 490.53x^{0.4562}$ $R^2 = 0.9949$	104.12	0.31
C150 - Zirconium Copper (Cold drawn, aged)	$y = 544.4x^{0.0476}$ $R^2 = 0.9728$	108.98	0.3
C230 - Red Brass, 85% (Cold drawn 14%)	$y = 550.24x^{0.3694}$ $R^2 = 0.9877$	102.74	0.34
C464 - Naval Brass (Annealed)	$y = 738.58x^{0.2368}$	96.53	0.28

	$R^2 = 0.9628$		
C510 - Phosphor Bronze, 5% A (Cold drawn 85%, spring)	$y = 614.73x^{0.0345}$ $R^2 = 0.9766$	107.56	0.341
C614 - Aluminum Bronze D (Annealed)	$y = 865.8x^{0.1371}$ $R^2 = 0.9341$	108.94	0.312
C655 - High Silicon Bronze A (Annealed, soft)	$y = 849.37x^{0.3906}$ $R^2 = 0.9789$	107.56	0.346
C715 - Copper Nickel 30% (Annealed)	$y = 774.01x^{0.3573}$ $R^2 = 0.9807$	151.69	0.32

Table: Ansys Material Inputs where K =Strength Coefficient, n = Strain hardening exponent

2.3 Post-Computation

After solving the analysis successfully, total deformation, equivalent stress, and force reactions were obtained. The load-displacement graphs are drawn using the force generated in the y-direction and its corresponding displacement table. The tangents are drawn towards the curve to get the two linear equations. These equations are used to compute yield force and, ultimately, the yield stress generated using a small punch testing apparatus. Ultimate tensile forces can also be extracted using the load-displacement table.

3. Results

3.1 Comparison between Yield Stress obtained by SPT and Tensile Test

	Yield Force (SPT) (N)	Yield Stress (SPT) = Yield Force/ t^2 (N/mm ²)	Yield Stress (Tensile test) (N/mm ²)
C102 - Oxygen Free	34.03	544.41	322.67
C122 - Phosphorus Deoxidized, High Residual Phosphorus	9.29	148.69	46.19
C150 - Zirconium Copper	58.00	928.07	410.93
C230 - Red Brass, 85%	16.37	261.84	89.63
C464 - Naval Brass	34.58	553.34	213.74
C510 - Phosphor Bronze, 5% A	67.43	1,078.87	496.42
C614 - Aluminum Bronze D	61.96	991.30	409.55
C655 - High Silicon Bronze A	22.70	363.20	166.85
C715 - Copper Nickel 30%	23.64	378.31	128.93

Table: Yield Stress Obtained by SPT and Tensile Test

The final equation that we get by curve-fitting the points is:

$$y = 0.4631x - 16.167$$

The R-Squared value is: $R^2 = 0.9474$ (This indicates a good curve fit)

Thus, the above Equation can be stated as:

$$P_y = 0.4631 (F_y/t^2) - 16.167$$

Where, P_y - Yield Stress obtained by Tensile Test, F_y - Yield Stress obtained by SPT

Fig: Yield Relations

3.2 Comparison of Ultimate Tensile Stress obtained by SPT and Tensile Test

	Ultimate Force (SPT) (N)	Ultimate Stress (SPT) = Yield Force/t ² (N/mm ²)	Ultimate Stress (Tensile test) (N/mm ²)
C102 - Oxygen Free	201.98	3231.68	333.7
C122 - Phosphorus Deoxidized, High Residual Phosphorus	170.71	2731.36	215.8
C150 - Zirconium Copper	285.38	4566.08	444.37
C230 - Red Brass, 85%	216.44	3463.04	278.55
C464 - Naval Brass	307.12	4913.92	436.44
C510 - Phosphor Bronze, 5% A	290.18	4642.88	553.65
C614 - Aluminum Bronze D	380.76	6092.16	573.64
C655 - High Silicon Bronze A	270.14	4322.24	423.34
C715 - Copper Nickel 30%	306.64	4906.24	398.52

Table: Ultimate tensile Stress obtained by SPT and Tensile Test

The final equation that we get by curve-fitting the points after neglecting errors is:

$$y = 0.0966x - 25.255$$

The R-Squared value is: $R^2 = 0.9043$ (This indicates a good curve fit)

Thus, the above Equation can be stated as:

$$P_u = 0.0966 (F_u/t^2) - 25.255$$

where, P_u - Ultimate Tensile Point using Tensile Test, F_u - Ultimate Tensile Point using SPT

Fig: Ultimate Tensile Stress Relations

Fig: Ultimate Relations Neglecting Errors

4. Conclusion

Small punch tests were performed by using miniature disk-shaped specimens for testing. The use of the current numerical modelling scheme for small punch testing is a creative strategy that will have an impact on model validation and calibration. The small punch test is the most effective as a model validation method as it has multi-axiality and loading history.

A new correlation between the yield stress of SPT and the yield stress of tensile test has been derived. Also, a correlation between the ultimate stress of SPT and the ultimate stress of the tensile test has been derived. The correlation shows a linear dependency between these two parameters, as also reported in another study.

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A Brief Author Biography

Jishnu Patil – Received his dual degree of Bachelor of Technology (B.Tech.) in Mechanical Engineering and Master of Business Administration (M.B.A.) in Technology Management from NMIMS University in 2020. During his undergraduate studies, he was actively involved in multiple design and fabrication projects, with a strong focus on mechanical systems optimization. He later pursued a Master of Science in Mechanical Engineering from the University of Michigan-Dearborn, MI, USA, where he expanded his knowledge in finite element methods, powertrains, mechanical testing, and optimized design. His academic interests lie in mechanical design, manufacturing optimization, and the integration of modern tools in engineering problem-solving.